

DIPLOMACY OF THE EMIRATE OF BUKHARA DURING THE REIGN OF AMIR NASRULLAH KHAN (RELATIONS BETWEEN IRAN)

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Abstract: This article is aimed at revealing Nasrullah Khan's tough foreign policy and skillful diplomatic qualities, and the fact that he made convenient and beneficial agreements with Iran for his benefit further increases his power. In the history of the Emirate of Bukhara, even though it has the name "bloody emir", it managed to solve political issues of important geopolitical importance in diplomatic matters.

Key words: Nasrullah Khan, Muhammadshah, Jozef Vulf diplomacy, ambassador, Marv.

He ascended the throne of Bukhara on Thursday, the end of Ramadan in 1828¹. Due to Amir Nasrullah Khan's strong policy, Russia, as the strongest among the rulers of the declining Khiva and Kokan khanates in Central Asia, appears to be the only threat to countries such as Great Britain.

In the history of the foreign policy of the Bukhara Emirate, diplomatic relations between the country of Iran also occupy an important place. Amir Nasrullah Khan's activities in strengthening diplomatic relations with Iran can be highlighted. Amir Nasrullah Khan, who is a serious threat to countries like Khiva and Kokan in Central Asia due to his constant struggles to achieve stability in domestic politics, his wars to strengthen the government, and his ruthlessness, conducts useful diplomatic relations with the Iranian state in foreign policy.

If we talk about the initial diplomatic relations and mutual agreements between the two countries, the ambassadors sent from Iran under the leadership of Mohammad Shah in 1844, their tasks are of special value. These ambassadors were assigned the task of solving a number of issues: discussing the issue of releasing prisoners held in Bukhara; Reaching a certain agreement on issues related to Marv region and Turkmens; Such as the positive resolution of the issue of the release of the British citizen Joseph Wolfe, who is in captivity in Bukhara²

¹ Ahmad Donish. Risola yohud mang'itlar xonadoni saltanatining qisqacha tarixi. – T.: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2014. B – 32,

² Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010. Б – 49-50.

Amir Nasrullah Khan's wars in his territory also take a lot of time, that is, he marches 32 times over Kitab and Shahrizabz for 30 years³. The reason for expanding the territory of the Bukhara Emirate is the desire to make friends with a common goal in foreign policy through the Iranian ambassadors. Referring to the results of the embassy in 1844, the Iranian ambassador pointed out that the captives kept in Bukhara are being kept in Bukhara based on ancient traditions and customs based on the fatwas of the scholars, and that the captives were not returned to Iran because they were bought for cash, and aimed at further strengthening mutual relations between the two countries in order to eliminate such legal problems. accepts the emir's proposals. Regarding the political situation in the Marv region, the Bukhara emir explained to him the complexity of the political situation in this region, emphasized that he was appointed at the request of the governor of Marv, emphasized that the Turkmen clans had organized actions against the Bukhara emirate, and said that it is necessary to restore the oasis of Marv, otherwise no one will be able to rule Marv

The most intense of the diplomatic debates in the country of Iran is related to British espionage in Bukhara. Colonel Stoddart and Captain Connolly were sent through Iran to carry out espionage in Central Asia, and these ambassadors were executed by Amir Nasrullah Khan. They send Joseph Wolfe, who uses Iran's mediation to free the two ambassadors, and imprison him as an accomplice of spies. The most intense of the diplomatic debates in the country of Iran is related to British espionage in Bukhara. Colonel Stoddart and Captain Connolly were sent through Iran to carry out espionage in Central Asia, and these ambassadors were executed by Amir Nasrullah Khan. They send Joseph Wolfe, who uses Iran's mediation to free the two ambassadors, and imprison him as an accomplice of spies. The emir and the Iranian ambassador send Subhonkulibek as ambassador to Iran with gifts. He is the Ambassador of Iran Joseph takes Woolf and Iranian prisoners and leaves Bukhara⁴. Establishing diplomatic relations with the Iranian state saved the life of the British ambassador. Based on this, Relations between Bukhara and Iran were much better, since the ambassador, who was seen as an English spy, was not easily released.

As one of the most acute issues in the relations between the Emirate of Bukhara and the state of Iran is the issue of captives, this factor was an obstacle

³ R. Shamsuddinov, O'. Ubaydullayev, Sh. Karimov. Vatan tarixi (XVI-XX asr boshlari). – T.: Sharq, 2020. B – 86.

⁴ Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010. Б – 50-51

to the development of the foreign political and diplomatic relations between the two countries. The nomadic tribes and clans, who did not obey either of the two countries, carried out various robberies on the caravan routes and in the border areas, and sold the captives in the markets of Bukhara and other cities. It was difficult to completely abolish the slave trade because of the interests of the parties involved in this form of human trafficking, that is, the seller and the receiver. In addition to the socio-political essence of this problem, there is also an ideological basis, which was determined by the differences between the Sunni and Shia sects. Taking into account that such an opinion belongs to a controversial debate, in order to establish peaceful relations between the two countries, the emir of Bukhara sent ambassadors to the Sultan of Turkey from time to time, tried to determine the legality of the issue and requested to send the works of great scholars and mujtahids in order to find a legal solution to it. Two ambassadors were entrusted by the emir to bring the sources of law that would allow to solve this legal problem⁵. It can be said that Nasrullah Khan has the ability to foresight, and he has a skillful policy so that diplomatic relations with Iran do not get negative. Solving the shortcomings in the relations between the two countries based on a well-thought-out political plan, including solving the religious issue in connection with the Sultan of Turkey, shows diplomatic respect and skill at the world level. He sought advice from the Turkish sultan, who received the status of caliph in the Islamic world without acting on his own in religious matters, and his skillful use of Sharia rules for his own benefit led to him occupying a special place among the emirs of Bukhara.

The period of Amir Nasrullah's reign has not been scientifically researched enough. Until now, scholars have conflicting and contradictory opinions about his personality. As one of the reasons for this, the fact that progressive and free-thinking people were persecuted by Amir Nasrullah and even killed in various ways is indicated many times in historical sources and scientific studies⁶. In conclusion, Nasrullah Khan was very active in diplomatic matters. He was able to resist as the most worthy opponent in Central Asia, which was a struggle between Russia and Great Britain. Although considered a "butcher emir" after much bloodshed during Nasrullah Khan's reign, he managed to resolve issues of geopolitical importance that were important in foreign political and diplomatic matters. Embassy relations with the Iranian state will improve during his tenure,

⁵ Ж.М.Шодиев. Бухоро амирлиги давлатчилигининг ривожланиши. – Тошкент.; ТДЮИ “Тезкор нашр марказида”. 2010. Б – 51

⁶ Jumanazar A. K. Buxoro ta'lim tizimi tarixi. – Toshkent.; Akademnashr, 2017 — 592-bet.

and political agreements and issues to be resolved will be drawn up for the benefit of both countries.

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